

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF BEAMS REINFORCED WITH LONGITUDINAL AND TRANSVERSE BFRP BARS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study comparing numerical and experimental results for beams reinforced with longitudinal and transverse BFRP bars tested under three-point flexure. A series of four beams containing two different reinforcement ratios are casted and tested. Experimental results were compared with a 3D FEM model developed using the software DIANA considering BFRP bars as embedded in concrete. The numerical simulations yielded accurate predictions for ultimate strength, crack patterns and demonstrate the importance of considering a bond slip rule for BFRP. Results are interesting to demonstrate that numerical models can accurately predict the behavior of beams using FRP materials.

KEYWORDS

BFRP rebar; RC beam; Flexural properties; Finite element analysis.

INTRODUCTION

To design a structure, many aspects must be taken in account, for example, applied loads, material resistance, construction method, etc. Conventional steel rebars are used in worldwide construction but they are prone to corrosion due to chloride presence and concrete carbonation. These phenomena cause deterioration of the structure, consequently reducing durability. Hence, the use of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) rebars as an alternative to steel has been gaining popularity.

FRP composites consist in combining two different materials, a reinforcing or fiber phase embedded into a matrix phase. The fibers provide strength and stiffness whereas the matrix, such as cured resin-like epoxy, holds the fibers in the intended position, providing structural integrity and shear transfer capability (Gangarao et al., 2007). Fibers commonly used to make FRP are glass (GFRP), aramid (ARFP) and carbon (CFRP). Recently basalt fibers have become commercially available as an alternative to glass fibers (Nanni et. al., 2014).

Mechanical behavior of FRP is different of conventional steel reinforcement, changing the design methodology. The main characteristics of BFRP are a linear stress-strain relationship and the elasticity modulus which is lower than the conventional steel bars. FRP materials have high strength in the direction of reinforcing fibers and are anisotropic, which affects shear strength, dowel effect and bond performance. Furthermore, FRP material do not yield, which means that the lack of ductility must be considered during the design procedure (ACI Committee 440, 2015).

Abed et. al. (2019) studied shear performance of BFRP reinforced beams with length of 2000mm without stirrups, considering different values for height and shear span, tested under 4 points for flexure. A numerical model developed using software package ABAQUS showed good agreement with experimental results. Huang and Dai (2021) also studied slabs, but with geopolymer concrete instead of conventional concrete, focuses on environmental friendliness. The authors observed that the specimen's failure was governed by shear compression or diagonal tension depending on the reinforcement ratio. A finite element model was implemented using ABAQUS with good prediction of the structural performance.

Cai et. al. (2017) analysed beams with engineered cementitious composite (ECC) and BFRP reinforcement. The authors first developed a numerical model using the software ATENA to compare with experimental results from literature. A good agreement between numerical and experimental results was observed.

The purpose of this study is to provide a contribution about the use of BFRP in beams through the comparison between experimental and numerical results. For this, four beams containing longitudinal and transverse BFRP reinforcement were tested under three-point flexure aiming to evaluate the flexure performance for two different reinforcement ratios. Experimental tests are compared with a numerical model developed in the software DIANA for load-deflection response, failure mode and crack pattern.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials

Concrete

Raw materials for manufacturing concrete are consisted of cement, coarse and fine aggregates. The cement is of type CPII-F for the local supplier Votorantim, produced in accordance with NBR 16697 (2018). The coarse aggregate is crushed granite with a maximum size of 9.5 mm, and river sand as fine aggregate. Coarse and fine aggregate are sourced from the region of Curitiba – Brazil and respect the provisions from NBR 7211 (2022).

The proportions cement: coarse aggregate: sand in the concrete are 1.00:2.16:1.81 by volume, and water/ cement ratio of 0.5, by weight. Fourteen concrete cylinders of 100 x 200 mm (diameter x height) are prepared during the fabrication of the beams to test compressive strength according NBR 5739 (2018). Concrete achieved an average compressive resistance of 26.25 MPa with a standard deviation of 3.51 MPa.

BFRP Rebars

BFRP bars supplied by Haizer Building Group, Brazil, are selected for this study. The bars have epoxy matrix and helical wrapped surface. For longitudinal reinforcement are used straight bars with diameters of 10 and 12 mm (Fig. 1a), and for stirrups, 4 mm bars, bent in factory before the resin cure process (Fig. 1b)

Figure 1: BFRP bars with helical wrapped surface

The supplier conducted tests to evaluate mechanical properties for the bars. Results for tensile strength and elastic modulus are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: BFRP mechanical properties

Diameter (mm)	Number of samples	Tensile strength (MPa)		Elastic modulus (GPa)	
		\bar{x}	s	\bar{x}	s
10	5	1012.92	36.70	52.58	2.46
12	5	1014.47	42.88	51.53	1.92

Test Specimens

Four beams with two different configurations using BFRP as longitudinal and transverse reinforcement are casted and tested under three-point flexure. The dimensions were 1100 x 100 x 200mm (length x width x depth) with a concrete cover of 15mm. Specimens are over-reinforced and designed following the provisions of ACI Committee 440 (2015). Nomenclature follows the form BDD.N, where DD is the rebar diameter (10 or 12mm) and N the specimen number (1 or 2). B10.1, for example, represents the first specimen for a beam reinforced with 10mm BFRP bars. Figure 2 shows details of the specimens and test setup, and Table 2 the reinforcement configuration.

Figure 2: Details of the specimen and test setup

Table 2: Reinforcement configuration

Specimen	Rebar diameter (mm)	ρ	ρ_b	Stirrups
		(%)	(%)	
B10	10	0.87	0.25	\emptyset 4mm @40mm
B12	12	1.26	0.24	\emptyset 4mm @37mm

ρ and ρ_b are the reinforcement ratio, and balanced reinforcement ratio, respectively.

Digital Image Correlation

Digital image correlation (DIC) is an optical and noncontact measurement technique that is used to measure displacements on the surface of an object of interest through the analysis of images taken by a digital camera. The displacement is then used to calculate the surface strain of an object of interest (Mahal et. al., 2015). For DIC work properly, it is necessary to prepare a surface with random pattern on the surface of the studied object. For this reason, all the beams are prepared with a white background followed by a random speckle pattern using a spray paint. To improve the pattern detection an extra light source is added to the DIC setup.

For image acquisition, a digital camera NIKON D7100 with lens AF-S Nikkor 18-300mm is placed perpendicular to the beam face. Due to the position of the beam in the hydraulic jack, only the half face was analysed as shown in Figure 3. After the acquisition, the image analysis was conducted using the software GOM Correlate.

Figure 3: Region of image acquisition for DIC

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

General description

Three-dimensional finite element (FE) model is developed to simulate the non-linear behaviour of beams reinforced with BFRP using the software DIANA version 10.3. Figure 4 shows the overall view of the FE model. Here, concrete, load plate and supports were modelled using a 20-node isoparametric element (CHX60) and BFRP rebars were treated as embedded. BFRP rebars and concrete share the same nodes, which means that a perfect bond is assumed. Interface elements with low elastic modulus in the horizontal direction were adopted between concrete and supports to avoid horizontal reactions due to beam deflection.

The load was applied under displacement control, in the same way the experimental test. Analysis was terminated after attainment a fixed displacement similar to the that obtained in the experiments.

A mesh sensitivity analysis was conducted to ensure convergence during analysis and minimizing computational time. For this purpose, different element sizes are tested before select the mesh configuration. After the mesh sensibility analysis, elements are set with 20mm and a load step of 0.2mm.

Figure 4: Finite element model

Material Properties

The total strain-based crack model is used for concrete with the smeared crack concept. In this approach the cracked solid is supposed to be a continuum starting from the notion of stress and strains

and permits a description in terms of stress-strain relations. Inside the smeared crack concept, it is possible to assign the crack orientation as fixed or rotating. This study adopted crack orientation as rotating, it means that the orientation co-rotate with the axes of principal strain, then is sufficient to specify non-linear stress-strain curves for the principal directions (Roots & Blaauwendraad, 1989).

The parabolic curve was adopted to describe the uniaxial compressive stress (f) – strain (α) relationship for concrete, shown in Figure 5a and explained by Eq. 1 to 4.

$$f = \begin{cases} -f_c \frac{1}{3} \frac{\alpha_j}{\alpha_{c/3}} & \text{if } \alpha_{c/3} < \alpha_j \leq 0 \\ -f_c \frac{1}{3} \left(1 + 4 \left(\frac{\alpha_j - \alpha_{c/3}}{\alpha_c - \alpha_{c/3}} \right) - 2 \left(\frac{\alpha_j - \alpha_{c/3}}{\alpha_c - \alpha_{c/3}} \right)^2 \right) & \text{if } \alpha_c < \alpha_j \leq \alpha_{c/3} \\ -f_c \left(1 - \left(\frac{\alpha_j - \alpha_c}{\alpha_u - \alpha_c} \right)^2 \right) & \text{if } \alpha_u < \alpha_j \leq \alpha_c \\ 0 & \text{if } \alpha_j \leq \alpha_u \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$\alpha_{c/3} = -\frac{1}{3} \frac{f_c}{E_c} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$\alpha_c = -\frac{5}{3} \frac{f_c}{E_c} = 5\alpha_{c/3} \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

$$\alpha_u = \alpha_c - \frac{3 G_{fc}}{2 h f_c} \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

Here, f_c is the ultimate concrete compressive strength, obtained by experimental tests, E_c is the elastic modulus, taken as 26,256 MPa, in accordance with ACI Committee 318, (2019). h is the element length and G_{fc} is the fracture energy in compression, adopted as 32,864 N/mm according to Nakamura & Higai (2001). The Poisson's ratio was taken as 0.2.

Constitutive law for concrete in tension was characterized by the curve proposed by Hordjik (Figure 5b). This model adopts a linear segment up to the maximum tensile strength followed by a softening function based on the concrete failure energy in tension (G_f). Tension resistance of concrete (f_t) is taken as 3.177 MPa, according to correlations presented in ACI Committee 318, (2019). G_f is adopted as 0.131 N/mm, obtained through FIB (2013).

a) Constitutive model in compression

b) Constitutive model in tension

Figure 5: Constitutive models for concrete (TNO DIANA BV, 2019)

BFRP is modelled as a linear elastic material with elastic modulus in accordance to test results. Stirrups with 4 mm diameter were not tested, then, the elastic modulus was taken equal to the 8mm rebar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Flexural Strength and load deflection

All beams are subjected to a three-point flexure test. Table 3 presents numerical and experimental results in terms of maximum loads and mid-span deflections, and Figures 6 and 7 the load-deflection curves.

Table 3: Comparison for maximum loads and deflections

Specimen	Maximum load (kN)			Deflection at peak (mm)		
	Experimental	Numerical	Predict / test	Experimental	Numerical	Predict / test
B10.1	69.84	79.15	1.13	16.47	17.00	1.03
B10.2	78.63	79.15	1.01	19.77	17.00	0.86
B12.1	89.33	88.50	0.99	17.6	13.40	0.76
B12.2	78.65	88.50	1.13	15.18	13.40	0.88

The load vs mid-span relationship in Figures 6 and 7 presents two different stages during loading. The first stage occurs between the beginning of the test until the crack load, with a linear load-deflection curve influenced by the concrete elastic modulus and tensile strength. In the second stage, from the first crack up to peak load, the beam stiffness decreases, but a larger reinforcement ratio led to small deflection under the same load, as expected. At the end of the second stage, the load suddenly dropped in beams reinforced with 10mm rebars, indicating a brittle failure of the specimen. Beams reinforced with 12mm rebars presented a less steep drop of the load after the peak, representing a more ductile failure, desirable when the specimen is designed to fail due concrete compression.

In terms of maximum load, predicted values are close with the test results. In mean values, numerical models overstated in 7% and 6% for beams reinforced with 10mm and 12mm rebars, respectively.

For displacement at peak, predict values are smaller than that obtained in experimental tests. Considering mean values, predicted displacements are understated in 5.5% for beams reinforced with 10mm rebars, and 18% for that with 12mm. This behaviour of the numerical model is due the assumption of perfect bond between BFRP bar and concrete, as can be observed in Figures 6 and 7 through a higher stiffness in the post-cracking branch. These observations imply that, for the studied beams, the consideration of a bond slip rule between concrete and BFRP is necessary to obtain more accurate results for displacements.

Figure 6: Load – deflection curves for B10 beams

Figure 7: Load – deflection curves for B12 beams

Crack Pattern and Failure Modes

The crack patterns of the specimens are shown in Figures 8 and 9 for beams reinforced with 10mm and 12mm rebars, respectively. For each specimen, the first crack appeared on the bottom, aligned with the load application. With increasing load, diagonal cracks emerged and developed towards the load point. Near the maximum capacity, concrete crush was found on the top, but the failure occurred due shear through the opening of an inclined crack.

Figure 8 compares numerical and experimental results for beams reinforced with 10mm rebars. The numerical model predicts one crack aligned with the load point, two main diagonal cracks, and also another small cracks due flexure on the bottom. In general, the numerical model presents fewer diagonal cracks than experiments, but even so it was able to predict the failure by shear.

For beams with 12mm rebars, shown in Figure 9, the number of cracks is similar between the numerical and experimental models, with a better agreement with beam B12.1 especially on the crack inclination. For these beams the numerical model also predicts correctly the failure mode by a diagonal crack.

In general, numeric models predicted adequately the failure modes and crack patterns in the specimens.

a) Numerical crack pattern for beams B10

b) Experimental crack pattern for beam B10.1

c) Experimental crack pattern for beam B10.2

Figure 8: Comparison between experimental and numerical crack pattern

a) Numerical crack pattern for beams B12

b) Experimental crack pattern for beam B12.1

c) Experimental crack pattern for beam B12.2

Figure 9: Comparison between experimental and numerical crack pattern

CONCLUSIONS

Based on a numerical and experimental study on beams reinforced with BFRP as longitudinal and transverse reinforcement tested under three-point flexure, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) The failure mode of all beams consisted in concrete crush on the load point region, followed by a inclined crack, which characterizes a failure controlled by shear, even with the presence of stirrups.
- (2) The finite element model provided good predictions for maximum load of all tested beams, overstating de value between 6% and 7% for beams reinforced with 10mm and 12mm rebars, respectively.
- (3) For deflection at the maximum load, the numerical model understated in 5.5% for beams with 10mm rebars and 18% for that with 12mm. In general, the load-displacement curve of the numerical model is stiffer than that observed in experiments. This occurs due the assumption of perfect bond between BFRP and concrete, indicating that the using of a bond slip rule is desirable to obtain a more accurate response.
- (4) Numeric models predicted adequately the failure mode due shear. For crack patterns the results for the stiffer beam, with 12mm rebars, are better than the predictions for the beam with 10mm.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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